

ANALYSIS

Using a dedicated adaptation financing process to close subnational adaptation finance gaps in Europe[☆]Kit England^a, Paul Watkiss^a, Alistair Hunt^{b,*}, Konstantinos Dellis^c, Sam Barrett^d, Richard Taylor^e, Stella Whittaker^f^a Paul Watkiss Associates, Oxford, UK^b University of Bath, UK^c Athens University of Economics and Business, Greece^d International Institute for Environment and Development, UK^e Stockholm Environment Institute (Oxford), UK^f Copenhagen Business School, Denmark

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ABSTRACT

There is a large finance gap between what countries and regions need for climate change adaptation and what is being supplied. Meeting regional adaptation needs is likely to require significant reform to subnational financing arrangements. In this context, institutions are developing new approaches, but these remain underexplored in the literature. In the mainstream climate finance discourse, the development of Adaptation Investment Planning (AIP) processes is emerging as a key focus for national governments – with methods emerging to translate high level ambitions into programmatic sets of bankable projects. Yet despite the importance of subnational governments in implementing adaptation, there has been little attention given to developing similar approaches at this level.

In the face of accelerating climate change risks, Europe is fostering new and innovative solutions to mobilise resources. To date, European subnational adaptive management cycles have had limited focus on addressing financing barriers. We highlight that by employing a welfare economics lens, it is possible to identify barriers to adaptation financing, and design dedicated AIP processes to address these. Drawing on the results of the Pathways2Resilience project and building on a review of 14 adaptation planning processes, we have developed a subnational Adaptation Investment Cycle and are currently testing this with 100 regions in Europe. The cycle links adaptation planning and decision-making with public financial management, investment management and development planning. We argue that this will enable subnational governments to build pipelines of adaptation investments and strengthen enabling environments, whilst also improving governance and facilitating wider financial reform. We conclude by evaluating limitations and recommending areas for further research.

1. Introduction

Whilst global mitigation efforts will help to reduce future impacts, the climate will continue to change towards the 2050s, and the world will need to scale-up adaptation efforts (IPCC, 2023). This scale-up will involve costs of adaptation, associated with the costs of planning, preparing for, facilitating, and implementing adaptation measures (IPCC, 2022a). At the global level, these anticipated adaptation costs - which are often reported as adaptation finance needs - are much higher than current adaptation finance flows, creating an adaptation finance gap

(UNEP, 2023). In Europe, analysis of current national adaptation plans with extrapolation indicates annual adaptation finance needs before 2030 of €18bn - €64bn – equivalent to between 0.1 and 0.4 % of EU GDP (World Bank, 2024).

In order to increase flows of adaptation finance, Adaptation Investment Planning (AIP) is being proposed to translate priorities in national adaptation plans into more programmatic pipelines and scale-up financing (Asian Development Bank, 2023; Hernández and Ceinos, 2025; IISD, 2022). Whilst the majority of AIP processes have focused on the national level, subnational (regional and local) governments and

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other non-state actors are crucial for implementation of effective adaptation, since they bring unique knowledge of local conditions and risks (Smith et al., 2025). Subnational governments often have mandated responsibility for delivering adaptation and are typically assigned responsibility for financing adaptation (De Mello and Martinez-Vazquez, 2022). Indeed, while all EU countries have national adaptation plans, 90 % of European adaptation measures within these plans are expected to be implemented at the local level (European Committee of the Regions, 2021). There is therefore considerable potential for subnational financing approaches to complement national initiatives.

Further, the level of regional development and the adaptive capacity of regions are closely related, affecting the ability to finance adaptation. More developed regions have greater absorptive and adaptive capacity since they can leverage a strong business demographic capable of delivering technical solutions required for climate adaptation, foster innovation, and support local and cross-regional innovation systems (Konrad and Thum, 2014; Rodriguez-Pose and Di Cataldo, 2015). This suggests that increasing access to adaptation (and therefore finance) may also have the potential to contribute to regional development, through supporting wider competitiveness, innovation, employment and equity (Gancheva et al., 2024) whilst there is emerging evidence that such investments also result in significant macroeconomic gains (Filatova et al., 2025; Mongelli et al., 2025)). It also implies that more direct intervention will be needed to support regions with lower adaptive capacity or economic development.

Europe’s current approach to subnational adaptation planning prioritises the use of adaptive management approaches - a cycle of application and learning that encourages future adjustments in response to new climate risk information (EEA, 2024). Historically these approaches have focused more on incremental adaptation, but there is now a focus on more transformational adaptation. The EU has launched a mission to creating 150 climate resilient regions and local authorities by 2030 in its Adaptation Mission (European Commission, 2021). Projects funded under the Mission are developing new tools and approaches to realise this goal, and this is leading to an evolution of current adaptation cycles: an example of which has been developed in the Pathways2Resilience (P2R) project and is shown in Fig. 1.

In this example, the adaptive management cycle includes visioning and ambition setting (Langendijk et al., 2025), which are then translated into programmatic pathways (rather than individual options), with a set of near-term actions to begin delivery. These cycles also include the analysis of enabling factors that run alongside these, moving the process from options appraisal to more systematic considerations. A final innovation – and the focus of this paper - is a more explicit consideration of adaptation economics and financing. These have historically been considered later in the cycle, if at all. (Watkiss and Preinfalk, 2022).

Alternative approaches to setting adaptation ambition impact the choice of actions, whilst the ability to achieve them is affected by barriers. Economic efficiency suggests that successful adaptation actions are those that maximise economic benefits whilst minimising the combined total of residual damages and adaptation costs, adjusted for distributional weighting across time and space (Cimato and Mullan, 2010; Fankhauser et al., 1999). Thus, barriers to adaptation and its financing comprise factors which hamper the achievement of optimal economic outcomes and cost minimisation. There are five broad groups of barriers, covering information, market failures, financial barriers, policy and governance barriers, and behavioural barriers (Paul Watkiss Associates and Frontier Economics, 2022; Watkiss and England, 2025). Principal amongst these barriers is the fact that there are often market failures operating on climate risks, adaptation effectiveness and benefits, (Pauw et al., 2022; Stoll et al., 2021), and that adaptation often has public good and non-market characteristics that result in low or no revenues (Bisaro and Hinkel, 2018). There are also instances of positive externalities creating low financial return but high economic return (Mortimer et al., 2020; Pauw et al., 2022). In relation to finance barriers, there are typically low or no revenues that can be attributed to climate risk reduction resulting in low rates of return or long paybacks of such investments (Cimato and Mullan, 2010; UNEP-FI, 2019). There are also a large number of other barriers and constraints including more practical issues that affect the bankability of adaptation, such as site specificity and low replicability (Mortimer et al., 2020), typically small investment size (IGCC, 2017), project complexity, and the number of actors and intermediaries involved (Mortimer et al., 2020).

These barriers manifest in challenges relating to definition of acceptable levels of risk and adaptation objectives, risk allocation and ownership between households, businesses and government, societal willingness to pay, financing strategies, enabling conditions, and outcome and value creation. Consequently, mobilising adaptation finance requires the development and application of a process which builds on the early stages of broader adaptation planning and explicitly addresses such barriers.

In this paper we utilise a review-based method to develop an adaptation financing process for regions and local authorities known as the Adaptation Investment Cycle (AIC). This cycle supports the broader adaptation planning cycle shown above. To inform this review, the guiding research question used was:

What current processes, guidance, tools, catalogues, strategies, activities, or actions can help local government, cities and regions in Europe to mobilise finance for equitable incremental and transformational adaptation to climate change?

This was then built upon using the authors’ expert judgements and wider input from within the Pathways2Resilience project to create the cycle. The cycle integrates economic principles explicitly in order to address barriers to mobilising adaptation finance. Section two outlines the methods used to undertake the review and develop the specific adaptation investment planning method for European regions. Section three presents the results of the review and the AIC, whilst section four evaluates the cycle’s contribution to bridging the adaptation finance gap. Section five provides overall conclusions and outlines areas for further research.

Fig. 1. The adaptation cycle of the Pathways2Resilience project. Source: (Pathways2Resilience, 2024).

2. Methods

The research focused on cities and regions in order to align with the aggregation focus of the EU Mission on Adaptation as well as to explicitly recognise that the political importance of the different tiers of subnational government varies across Europe.

We adopted a narrative review method. To increase robustness, we borrowed elements of a scoping review in line with the process set out in the JBI Manual for Evidence Synthesis (Aromataris and Munn, 2020). This choice of method was based on the following reasons.

- **Appropriateness** – the context specific nature of adaptation financing, as well as the varying range of solutions and approaches made an initial mapping of the literature more appropriate.
- **Solution-oriented focus** - The solution-oriented nature and ambition of the EU’s Adaptation Mission suggested a focus on ‘on the ground’ solutions rather than the academic literature.
- **State of adaptation finance literature** - The adaptation finance literature is an emerging space, making it more suited to a narrative or scoping review. Discussion with the eight adaptation experts, and initial searches, indicated that much of the literature was grey in nature.
- **Time** – The relatively short window afforded for the study meant a screening approach could be used to identify the most important components of the literature.

As a consequence, rather than adopting a full screening approach, we performed a simplified approach, rapidly screening documentation using the scoping criteria as a guide to select a final set of literature.

The development of the AIC consisted of five stages and is shown in Fig. 2 below:

1. The study undertook a high-level scan of adaptation finance literature to gain an overview of the topic. This provided a set of literature, identified the key expert institutions and how relevant knowledge was structured. Given the nascent stage of the adaptation finance literature, the academic literature search was complemented with searches of the grey literature, along with searches of conference proceedings and targeted websites, and discussion with eight expert contacts. The study used tailored web searches of Google for grey literature and Google Scholar for academic literature, conference proceedings from Adaptation Futures and the European Conference on Climate Adaptation, and known websites associated with adaptation and its financing, and discussions with the expert contacts.
2. We used keyword searches, snowballing and suggestions from eight experts in the field to identify a body of literature which contained adaptation finance processes. The search strategy used high level search terms (such as adaptation finance), and more specific case-based examples, to identify a long list of potential literature, including combinations of adaptation keywords with (a) planning keywords and (b) finance-related keywords. For example, we searched for ‘adaptation financ* AND green budgeting’. These are outlined in Table 1 below:

Searches were concluded when they reached thematic saturation. A literature review protocol was used to decide which literature to include or exclude. This is shown in Table 2.

The literature was reviewed and led to the creation of a final list, comprising 14 adaptation finance processes (in supplementary Table 1).

Table 1

Illustrative themes and keywords used in the literature review.

Theme	Keyword longlist (combined in searches)
Regional Adaptation Finance	Adaptation finance, Incremental, transformational, justice, equity, public, public-private, blended, leveraging, crowding in, funding, resilience, process, framework; regions; investment; bankable
Regional Adaptation Planning	Process, implementation, equity, finance, resilience, roadmap
Enabling conditions to mobilise finance	Costs, benefits, capacity, green budgeting, Monitoring, Evaluation, Learning, increasing,

3. The 14 identified adaptation finance processes identified in 3) were evaluated. A SWOT analysis was undertaken for each in relation to their potential as capacity building resources to mobilise finance, with the authors listing out the strengths and weaknesses, as well as the opportunities and threats presented by each process. This was based on their expert judgement. The results of the analysis were summarised into an assessment of their relevance to an adaptation finance process for regions.

4. The SWOT results were synthesised into an overall series of considerations for an adaptation finance process – focusing on objectives and scope, content, approach, attributes and look and feel. These were used to derive a set of hallmarks of adaptation planning processes, shown in Table 3.

5. The study used the insights from this review process, alongside the authors’ own expert judgement and experience, and lessons learnt from development work on the wider Regional Resilience Journey (Di Fant et al., 2023; Warren et al., 2023), as shown in Fig. 1, to develop and structure the adaptation finance process and AIC. This included discussions amongst the authors and the wider P2R consortium members to identify the relevant activities, their specifics and their ordering and alignment, as well as the relevant inputs and outputs related to the wider adaptation planning cycle developed within Pathways2Resilience, to ensure they were credible but were also mindful of the capacity of participating regions.

3. Results

3.1. Identified adaptation finance processes and their characteristics

The fourteen frameworks – listed in Supplementary Table 1 - were reviewed and evaluated for relevance to creating a European adaptation finance process for subnational governments. The heterogeneity of approaches made it challenging to generate common insights, but key findings included:

Outputs / outcomes - The frameworks target an array of different decision types for adaptation financing. This includes improvement of adaptation capabilities (Adaptation Scotland, 2019), the creation of a standalone Investment Plan (NetZeroCities, 2022), integration into existing adaptation strategies (EEA, 2024), integration into NDCs (CDKN and Ricardo, 2016) or a focus on bankable projects (ASAP, 2022; GIZ, 2019; Wise et al., 2022). One process combined a focus on adaptation capabilities with development of a strategy (Smart Mature Resilience, 2018). One combined enhancement of an adaptation strategy with a dedicated investment plan. (Tall et al., 2021). None of the processes provide a concrete approach for subnational (regional or provincial) governments to produce investment plans.

Addressing finance barriers – Nine of the processes included

Fig. 2. Adaptation Investment Cycle development process. Source: Authors.

Table 2
Criteria for the literature review. Source: Authors.

Included	Criteria type	Excluded	Criteria type
Local municipalities and regional municipalities within Europe	Population and condition	Adaptation planning guidance which didn't include a substantive finance component	Study design
Documents focusing on either incremental or transformational adaptation	Study design	Developing country studies mainly/solely reliant on global financing sources (e.g., Green Climate Fund, Adaptation Fund).	Population and condition
Documents focused on challenges or solutions to mobilising public and private finance	Study design	Studies focused solely on adaptation outside Europe with limited transferable lessons	Population and condition
Approaches focusing on financing across all stages of maturity	Study design	Studies in languages other than English	Study design
Documents focusing on tools and approaches to mobilise adaptation finance	Population and condition	Studies focusing mainly/wholly on mitigation	Study design
Studies focusing on equity and/or just resilience	Study design	Studies solely focused on adaptation finance as a barrier or constraint	Study design
Studies focused on 'enabling conditions/ environments' for mobilising adaptation finance (even if not at regional level)	Study design	Studies outside the Scope of the Mission's Key Community Systems	Population and condition
Studies focused on financing of adaptation projects, programmes, or strategies	Population and condition	Studies focused solely on UNFCCC processes	Population and condition
Studies that include case studies / best practice examples	Study design	Articles in draft or those inaccessible online (paywall, or unobtainable)	Study design
Documents that include sources or instruments for adaptation finance	Study design	Adaptation when not related to climate change Different geographical definition of region (e.g., globally)	Study design
Studies that address barriers identified in D5.1	Study design	Studies older than 7 years (2015 onwards)	

discussion of the challenges associated with adaptation finance, but only two explicitly set out how they address barriers to adaptation finance (ASAP, 2022; Wise et al., 2022) which identify economic and coordination barriers, as well as knowledge and evidence barriers, and provide approaches which seek to overcome them that involve more detailed project development approaches (e.g. modifying the scale or scope of projects, or considering benefits and beneficiaries).

Focus on public and/or private finance –The majority (seven) of processes focused on both public and private funding, including their interdependencies. Five focused primarily on public funding or financing. Only two processes focused solely on private sector finance (England and Murtagh, 2022; GIZ, 2019).

Use of transformative finance approaches – There is limited emphasis on the use of transformative finance approaches (defined here as new instruments or models to scale up adaptation or promote innovative and systemic adaptation, in line with Watkiss and Khosla, 2021 –

Table 3
Hallmarks of a robust Adaptation Investment Planning process and potential contents. Source: Authors.

Hallmark	Description
Purpose and principles	
<u>Purpose</u>	Adaptation Investment Planning (AIP) process should contain a set of steps which enables users to translate the high-level ambitions of a Climate Resilience or Adaptation Strategy into packages of bankable investments for delivery. These should be sequenced across budgetary cycles to address fiscal space constraints and maximise economic benefits. The AIP processes should be aligned with the development of an overall Climate Resilience Strategy or adaptation plan, as well as broader fiscal planning, rather than a stand-alone process.
<u>Principles</u>	
Integrative, systemic and transformative	Capability-maturity matrix approaches (Adaptation Scotland, 2019; UNDP, 2017) suggest the AIP should seek to be integrative – working within existing institutional arrangements and decision-making approaches – and ambitious, delivering at-scale through programmatic or transformative approach rather than being project-focused. This should be aligned with wider finance and governance systems (mainstreaming) and with the relevant responsible actors (e.g., finance departments in regional government). They should also seek to create wider shifts in attitudes and perceptions. They should include analytical approaches which seek to understand and address systemic risks and effects (Wise et al., 2022) These approaches should also integrate adaptation finance in other regional government roles, such as procurement, or direct provision of services, as well as wider place leadership (as in Boukerche et al., 2021). Finally, the approach should seek to be scaled and replicated across regions and governments to shift a focus to more systemic and transformative change (as advocated in (Mills-Novoa et al., 2025).
Equitable	An AIP should have justice and equity as a core consideration, throughout the process (ASAP, 2022), including in diagnostics and evidence gathering, generation and evaluation of options, identification and assessment of distributional effects of climate risks and adaptation packages, and the alignment of investment approaches, as well as in the consideration of sources and instruments. Additionally, involving those disproportionately affected by the risk or adaptation should have a role in the decision-making process. (Wise et al., 2022)
Open and transparent	The AIP should be made public to allow development banks, investors, and the private sector to identify opportunities to participate in adaptation funding and financing (Tall et al., 2021), and to raise awareness amongst citizens.
Contents and outputs	
Objectives	The AIP should clearly describe its main objective, as well as secondary objectives or benefits from its use (e.g., building skills and competencies, or informing others of investment needs).
Outputs	The main output should be a dedicated Adaptation Investment Planning document, supported by a pipeline of bankable projects, and an action plan for its implementation. (Boukerche et al., 2021; CDKN and Ricardo, 2016; Tall et al., 2021). The document should include an <u>investment-ready pipeline</u> of near-term projects or programmes which are priorities for funding or financing. Their characteristics should be described, as well as the economic and financial attractiveness, and the envisaged funding or financing approach, with appropriate sources, instruments and business models identified. The AIP document should identify <u>enabling conditions</u> that will help implement or scale-up adaptation financing (or prerequisites for certain pipeline investments). (NetZeroCities, 2022) These may include details relating to governance,

(continued on next page)

Table 3 (continued)

Hallmark	Description
	resources, knowledge and data, skills, policy and regulation (Brullo et al., 2024). The output should also acknowledge the role of policy at local, national and supra-national level and should encourage engagement with actors at different levels as necessary.
Delivery approach	The plan should set out a clear delivery approach (e.g. via a stylised diagram), showing how the combined actions, sources and instruments, governance mechanisms and enabling conditions will mobilise the resources.
Economic framing and rationale	The process should set out a strategic economic rationale to frame the investment approach (Resch et al., 2017) supported through calculating potential avoided economic losses and damages, and associated fiscal benefits (European Commission, 2023; Resch et al., 2017; UNDP, 2017).
Prioritisation and sequencing approach	The plan should include a process for prioritisation and sequencing, recognising the need to shortlist packages of measures (Wise et al., 2022) based on magnitude and timing of risk, and economic, financial and political factors.
Monitoring and Evaluation	An AIP process should identify a set of metrics, or key performance indicators (KPIs) to allow evaluation of progress against objectives and to foster transparency. This will also enhance accountability by increasing the overall amount of information available to politicians, NGOs, and other interested parties.
Process Characteristics	
Common but flexible approach	AIP should follow a standardised process but should be flexible enough to account for different regional and local contexts. (Adaptation Scotland, 2019; England and Murtagh, 2022; Smart Mature Resilience, 2018). This will ensure that the process will be locally relevant whilst, allowing comparability, knowledge exchange and learning. Standardisation will also enhance engagement of funders or financiers by allowing easier comparability and/or aggregation across jurisdictions.
Exploratory	AIPS should explore the full range of adaptation and financing options – with diverse sources and instruments for financing - early in the adaptation strategy process to ensure the proposed options have credible funding and financing approaches. (Wise et al., 2022)
Aligned with existing public processes	For fiscal and economic credibility, an AIP should align with the wider public financial management (PFM) frameworks and public investment management (PIM) frameworks (UNDP, 2017). This ensures that projects requiring public support assess value for money and fit with established processes for prioritising, and approval of, investment or spending.
Maximise private sector roles	The process should explicitly consider and define the role the private sector could play in delivering the plan in individual sectors, as well as their relative roles as funders, financiers or delivery agents. (Tall et al., 2021)
Alignment with green budgeting	An adaptation finance process can benefit from, and support, national and regional green (climate) budgeting processes. Tracking expenditure through Green budgeting can improve understanding of existing spend, whilst adaptation planning can help support tagging of relevant budget lines. (CDKN and Ricardo, 2016; England and Murtagh, 2022; OECD, 2022; Resch et al., 2017)
Iterative	The size and nature of the tasks required to develop an AIP suggest the process will evolve over time and iterative approaches should therefore be integrated with cycles of learning (EEA, 2024).
Buy-in	An early emphasis should be placed on securing high-level authority and strategic buy-in. (ASAP, 2022; UNDP, 2017)
Inclusive	Any process should be inclusive, encouraging widespread engagement and involving a wide variety of potential beneficiaries and actors in development, particularly the private sector. (CDKN and Ricardo,

Table 3 (continued)

Hallmark	Description
	2016; Tall et al., 2021). There should be a particular emphasis on involving those most vulnerable to climate change (ASAP, 2022). However, the range and type of actors involved is not likely to be the same at each stage of a process, suggesting the need to actively consider the types of actors to involve at each stage.
Supporting conditions	
Governance	Since developing an AIP integrates into institutional governance and processes, approaches to governing its development should ensure decision makers feel authorised, equipped, and supported, to be part of – and in specific areas move beyond - their existing decision contexts. The process also needs to ensure coordinated and strategic efforts to develop multi-sectoral and multi-level governance (to address coordination failures) (UNDP, 2017; Wise et al., 2022). In addition, it should include a degree of ‘realpolitik’ – emphasising the practical considerations that are likely to make an adaptation financing process successful, based on real world experiences of how decisions are made in the relevant context. (CDKN and Ricardo, 2016; Resch et al., 2017)
Regional capabilities and maturity	The ability to develop an AIP is in part down to institutional capabilities. It is important that a public institution understands its current capabilities and puts in place the capacity building and institutional strengthening required to allow the process (e.g., a structured team, sub, teams, working groups, well defined governance and roles and responsibilities, training and an available budget), to proceed within the required timescales. (Adaptation Scotland, 2019; CDKN and Ricardo, 2016; Smart Mature Resilience, 2018; UNDP, 2017)

for example the use of climate resilience districts (California Senate, 2022)). The majority of frameworks do not seek to use transformative finance approaches that support the development of new sources and instruments. These approaches also seek to change the wider system context, such as the governance processes, and how cross-sectoral investment decisions are made. However, four processes did include some emphasis on processes to support new or innovative sources and instruments – for example through aligning project development and financing approaches, through the variation and adjustment of project scopes and financing requirements.

Equity and Justice – Whilst many of the processes referred to vulnerability to climate change risks, only four processes included a dedicated focus on justice and equity (ASAP, 2022; Boukerche et al., 2021; European Commission, 2023; UNDP, 2017). This seems surprising given the distributional impacts of climate risk and adaptation (e.g. see Watkiss et al., 2016) but is likely to reflect the complexity of both climate justice and adaptation finance (IPCC, 2022b), and the novel nature of both domains in adaptation practice.

Type of processes – The frameworks employ a variety of processes – five provide step by step approaches whilst two (Resch et al., 2017; Wise et al., 2022) are more flexible – outlining key activities but without any prescriptive order. Three employ capability-maturity models (Adaptation Scotland, 2019; England and Murtagh, 2022; UNDP, 2017) that iteratively improve capabilities over time. Within these, the Adaptation Scotland and IEMA frameworks embed financing as part of a wider set of adaptation planning activities for public institutions, whilst the UNDP process focuses on integrating adaptation finance needs into existing finance frameworks. Only one highlights hallmarks or characteristics, citing what good projects look like (ASAP, 2022). Finally, one framework employed multiple approaches - ICLEI’s European Resilience Management Guideline (Smart Mature Resilience, 2018) - combines a step-by-step approach with a capability-maturity matrix.

The full results are shown in supplementary table 1.

3.2. Hallmarks of a robust adaptation investment planning process

The SWOT undertaken above generated a number of insights about the state of the art of adaptation finance processes, relating to their scope, objectives and design. These insights – or hallmarks – are a specific outcome of the ex post evaluation of existing adaptation finance processes. They are subjective and depend on the reviewers’ expert judgement and so should be seen as indicative. They were then used as the starting point for the creation of the AIC and are reported in Table 3 below:

3.3. The adaptation investment cycle

The final Adaptation Investment Cycle, derived from the review of adaptation finance processes and the associated hallmarks, as well as discussions with the wider Pathways2Resilience consortium members leading the development of the adaptation planning cycle, is shown below. The diagram (Fig. 3) shows the cycle mapped onto Pathways2Resilience’s adaptation planning cycle, known as the Regional Resilience Journey:

The cycle aims to help regions mobilise the resources to deliver their transformative Climate Resilience Strategies and Innovation Agendas. The six steps of the cycle include 18 individual tasks set out in Table 4. By following the phases and tasks, subnational governments can develop a programmatic pipeline of bankable projects and actions to improve the enabling conditions for adaptation.

Equity and justice considerations are incorporated across the six phases. These include an evaluation of the distributional impacts of extreme weather and climate change (1.2), as well as the impacts of adaptation. It also encourages the use of ethical considerations in the selection of additional sources and instruments (Task 2.2) – considering the potential for sources to invest or finance in activities that run counter to organisational policies or values, or the use of instruments that disadvantage particularly vulnerable groups. The potential for contributing to justice and fairness is included in the evaluation of the longlist

of options (Task 3.1), whilst distributional implications of individual actions is encouraged in the assessment of the economic and financial case (Task 4.1) well as in the financial models (Task 4.2). Furthermore, the process encourages the use of procedural justice by advocating that those involved in undertaken the AIP process include those most likely to be disproportionately affected.

3.4. Results from early applications

While the application of the cycle is at an early stage, and prevents comprehensive analysis, there are signs that the process is useful. The authors have been supporting four regions to apply the AIC: Ithaka, (Greece), Arnhem and Nijmegen (Netherlands), Marche (Italy) and London (UK). To date the regions have undertaken activities in Phase 1 and 2, but results are promising.

For London, in undertaking Phase 1, the region was supported to cost the economic impacts of the 2022 heatwave (England et al., 2025), whilst in Phase 2, it identified a range of existing sources of finance that could be scaled, such as Community Municipal Investments and parking revenues. In Ithaka, consideration of additional sources of finance has led for calls for new powers to implement tourism taxes to support local adaptation (Οικονομικός Ταχυδρόμος, 2025). In Marche, the region has identified a range of barriers to using new sources of finance, such as the political will to implement new taxes to fund adaptation shortfalls and it has also begun exploring new funding and financing approaches for a managed retreat pathway – one of its three priority areas of focus.

Prior to the Pathways2Resilience project, the authors worked with Glasgow City Region and EIT Climate-KIC on an early AIP to develop an early Resource Mobilisation Plan (Watkiss and Khosla, 2021) in support of its Adaptation Strategy and Action Plan (Climate Ready Clyde, 2021). This plan was subsequently evaluated against the AIC and its phases (Dellis et al., 2025), and is reproduced in Table 5. This work also analysed the finance mobilised since its adoption. The analysis found that Glasgow City Region has adopted many of the approaches set out in early phases of the Adaptation Investment Cycle (see below), leveraged

Fig. 3. The Pathways2Resilience Adaptation Investment Cycle. Source: England et al., 2024.

Table 4
Phases, descriptions and tasks of the P2R Adaptation Investment Cycle, and the associated finance barriers addressed. Source: Authors.

Phase	Description	Tasks	Types of barriers addressed
1. Define context and set climate resilience objectives	Define the approach to developing the Investment Plan, set objective(s) for the plan, understand the financial and economic context, and develop a positive financial and economic narrative for adaptation investment	1.1 Identify policy and financing context 1.2 Gather baseline economic and financial evidence 1.3 Develop climate resilience objectives and economic rationale	Information, economic, policy and governance, behavioural
2. Address strategic financing barriers	Document existing finance sources and instruments used for regional adaptation, identify additional possible sources and instruments that could be used, and identify the associated barriers and solutions to facilitate their rollout	2.1 Catalogue existing sources and instruments 2.2 Identify additional sources, instruments and barriers 2.3 Expand financing options	Information, financial, policy and governance, economic, behavioural
3. Define investment needs and strategies	Estimate the emerging costs and of the pathways in the Climate Resilience Strategy and develop initial strategic investment approaches for key hazards, sectors, or risks. Identify benefits of adaptation and type (public or private), as well as co-benefits	3.1 Longlist adaptation options and assess economic and financial costs and benefits 3.2 Prioritise and sequence adaptation options into sets of pathways 3.3 Develop Investment Strategies for preferred pathways	Information, economic, financial
4. Develop and build investment plan and project pipeline	Build project pipeline with investment-level analysis of costs and benefits, and business models, and develop an action plan for enabling conditions	4.1 Build specific economic and financial case for investments 4.2 Identify financial models for the near-term actions in packages 4.3 Decide on bankable priorities, future investments and enabling conditions	Policy and governance, economic, financial, behavioural
5. Matchmake for bankable investments	Implement near-term investments and further develop activities, value propositions and business models of projects, and associated arrangements to raise and distribute financing of future investments.	5.1 Define project and baseline financial and economic merits 5.2 Co-design value proposition and business model 5.3 Develop financial structuring and execution plan	Policy and governance, behavioural, financial, economic, information
6. Monitor, report, learn and reflect	Develop the tracking and reporting process and metrics and set in place tracking systems to measure	6.1 Identify metrics. and monitor and disclose progress	Information, behavioural

Table 4 (continued)

Phase	Description	Tasks	Types of barriers addressed
	progress as implementation begins. Undertake evaluation of the AIP process and identify learning for improvement.	6.2 Report on privately funded projects in line with financing requirements 6.3 Conduct a learning and reflection session on the AIP process	

an additional £1.4 m towards capacity building and implementation planning, designed high level innovative financing solutions and committed to establishing an adaptation finance lab.

However, there were gaps in later phases, including matchmaking for bankable projects, and limited finance-related monitoring, evaluation, reflection and learning. This suggests the approach has been valuable, and further work is planned to update and revise the Resource Mobilisation Plan. Whilst these developments are by no means conclusive, they highlight AIPs are encouraging new activities and approaches which are diversifying sources and instruments, and addressing barriers to mobilising finance, but also that such approaches need effective capacity building and training to foster their adoption.

4. Discussion

The AIC offers a process to finance transformative long-term Climate Resilience Strategies and their near-term actions for 100 subnational governments in Europe. As such it should be seen as a more systemic intervention – rather than a focus on individual adaptation projects - which offers new routes to address many of the commonly cited barriers to public and private adaptation finance. The process itself includes novel approaches and features which should help boost and supply adaptation finance.

4.1. Novel AIC features that enhance quality and quantity of finance

Seven novel features in the AIC that support successful financing are the i) integration into existing institutional arrangements, ii) economic and financial framing, iii) the prioritisation and sequencing processes, iv) the emphasis on climate justice, v) the potential reframing attitudes of decision makers, vi) optimization of the role of public finance, and vii) contributing to sustainable finance initiatives.

4.1.1. Integrating into existing institutional arrangements and governance processes

The AIP process improves the likelihood of financing an overall adaptation or resilience strategy through the broad integration and mainstreaming of adaptation investment into existing institutional arrangements and governance processes. This happens in three main ways. First, the process situates adaptation investment within the broader regional development context, identifying economic social and environmental objectives, and planned investments, to identify opportunities to align adaptation with broader development goals, either through climate proofing of investments such as infrastructure or complementary adaptation investments which support wider activities.

Second, the broader integration with public financial management processes (such as budget cycles), as well as public investment management processes helps focus and optimise the development of pipelines, ensuring investments are economically efficient and offer good value for money whilst accounting for practical considerations such as available fiscal space. The preparation of a publicly available pipeline of investments also integrates into typical economic development approaches, improves the visibility of investment opportunities for finance

Table 5

Mapping of coverage of Glasgow City Region's Adaptation Investment approach against the stages of the Adaptation Investment Cycle. Source: [Dellis et al., 2025](#).

		Documents			
		Adaptation Strategy and Action Plan	Economic and financial case	Resource Mobilisation Plan	Innovation Portfolio
AIC Stages	Phase 1: Define Investment Context and Set Objectives	X	X		
	Phase 2: Address Strategic Financing Barriers			X	
	Phase 3: Define investment needs and strategies	X		X	X
	Phase 4: Compile Investment Plan and Pipeline				
	Phase 5: Matchmake for bankable investments			Partial - high level finance approaches.	
	Phase 6: Monitor, report, learn and reflect				

and investment entities with interest in the region.

Finally, this approach aligns with the range of roles that are played by subnational governments in adapting to climate change, as consumers of goods and services, providers of goods and services, fund-raisers, regulators and convenors ([Boukerche et al., 2021](#)).

4.1.2. Economic and financial framing

The AIC employs an economic (welfare) framing of adaptation, helping set the economic costs of adaptation against the costs of climate change. This demonstrates how adaptation meets broader economic and social policy goals as well as strengthening public financing arrangements and potential fiscal benefits. For example, adaptation can improve regional economic performance by reducing the adverse impacts of heat on labour productivity ([Gosling et al., 2018](#)). It can also help reduce future chronic and one-off cost pressures on municipal finance and wider public institutions from reducing expenditure associated with climate shocks ([Avgousti et al., 2023](#); [Gilmore et al., 2022](#); [Shi et al., 2023](#)). The first stage of the AIC focuses on identifying and communicating these benefits to underline the positive economic role of adaptation.

While the economic return is critical for public projects, and associated public investment management prioritisation, it does not provide information on the financial sustainability or financial return of adaptation.

Therefore, the economic analysis is complemented with a financial analysis which looks at the potential revenue generation and cash flow potential of adaptation. This can help with the public financing but more importantly, it can identify where there is potential for the private sector to invest in adaptation.

4.1.3. Using economic and political criteria for prioritisation and sequencing adaptation

The process explicitly acknowledges that subnational governments will have to prioritise investments, due to realistic issues and constraints of limited budgetary resources, limited fiscal space and the need to demonstrate economic and financial value relative to other competing (non-climate) priorities. Therefore, it includes prioritisation tasks that take account of economic, financial, and political criteria, but also urgency and timing. The Investment Cycle includes phases and tasks which first use economic criteria in the shortlisting of adaptation options through a multi-criteria analysis. These shortlisted options are prioritised and sequenced over time based on urgency of when actions are needed or can be economically justified ([Tröltzsch et al., 2016](#); [Watkiss and Betts, 2021](#)), recognising that this sequencing can significantly affect the economic viability of programmatic investments ([Haasnoot et al., 2020](#)). In subsequent stages, the process thoroughly examines the economic and financial case for individual investments, and whether these are sufficient to pass the PIM criteria for public investment, or the financial viability to justify private sector interest.

4.1.4. Consideration of climate justice and equity issues

A third novel aspect is the consideration of climate justice throughout the process. It is well established in the literature that climate change affects individuals and organizations differentially, based on the combination of the hazards, exposure to those hazards and their relative vulnerability ([European Environment Agency, 2025](#); [IPCC, 2022a](#); [Lindley et al., 2011](#); [Watkiss et al., 2016](#)), and that these differential impacts also arise from historical injustices and unequal power arrangements. Similarly, differential impacts of climate change can also arise from alternative and procedural aspects of adaptation policies and responses ([Lager et al., 2023](#)).

Fair or just responses can be understood according to principles of distributive (the allocation of burdens and benefits amongst individuals, nations and generations) and procedural justice, but also recognition of, and respect for, engagement with diverse cultures and perspectives. ([IPCC, 2022a](#)).

Without consideration of equity in adaptation, existing inequalities may be reinforced, or new inequalities may arise, yet many vulnerable groups are only considered in impact assessment, with more limited consideration in adaptation measures, M&E or participation ([EEA, 2022](#)).

In response to these challenges, the Adaptation Investment Planning process mainstreams climate justice considerations across its phases and tasks. Examples include considering the impacts on the most vulnerable in collating early evidence of historic economic and financial impacts, as well as in future climate risk assessments, and inclusion of distributional impacts in appraisal of adaptation options. It also advocates for adequate consideration of procedural and recognition justice issues when designing governance mechanisms for development and approval of AIPs.

4.1.5. Reframing attitudes and perceptions of decision makers on adaptation investment

By framing adaptation and resilience within the wider economic and fiscal policy context, encouraging an economic rationale for adaptation and setting the cost of action against existing and projected future economic costs, and potential fiscal benefits, the AIC facilitates a shift in the perception of adaptation from a cost to a prudent investment. Doing so also shows how adaptation is positively linked to achievement of regional development objectives.

By working through the range of investment needs and potential investment strategies (along with appropriate sources and instruments), the process addresses common barriers to adaptation financing, focusing subnational governments on a broader array of approaches than defaulting to use of own resources or public grants. This can crowd in new actors and diversify and scale the sources of finance and instruments across the public and private sectors. This supports effective allocation of risk ownership and financing responsibilities (e.g. ([World Bank Group, 2019](#)).

Furthermore, the iterative nature of the process encourages a shift in

the political economy – relating to who is responsible for risks and who pays for adaptation amongst regional governments, firms and households. As Investment Plans are prepared and improved, institutions can move from a focus on individual projects to a longer term, programmatic societal / area-based response. In doing so, the full scale of adaptation investment needs will become apparent, and the attitudes and willingness of stakeholders to fund different approaches and split the balance between public and private sectors may change.

4.1.6. Optimizing the role of public finance for adaptation

The focus on meeting Public Financial Management (PFM) and Public Investment Management (PIM) criteria and working within the available fiscal space also focuses attention on the need to make best use of limited public funds and competing priorities. It puts more focus on the type of adaptation intervention and associated benefits streams, i.e., whether in market and non-market sectors, whether it is supporting public or private goods, and whether there are limited or potential financial returns which could encourage or incentivise private sector action. Doing so increases the potential to use public funds more strategically, focusing on identifying where there are opportunities to leverage and crowd-in private finance., either through the creation of enabling conditions to facilitate private sector investment (such as guarantees, de-risking mechanisms or policy and regulation, or provision of information), and through the use of blended finance approaches, public private partnerships or incentives to create returns. Doing so maximises the potential use of as well as ensuring that public funds focus on the provision of public goods.

4.1.7. Contributing to sustainable finance initiatives

Adaptation Investment Planning also offer a helpful complement to the emerging sustainable finance initiatives aimed at encouraging adaptation. It is increasingly understood that climate change represents a risk to financial institutions and firms (Climate Change Committee, 2023).

In response, central banks are increasingly assessing the implications of climate change on the financial system (Network for Greening the Financial System, 2022). At the same time regulators are placing disclosure requirements onto financial institutions and listed companies to assess their exposure to physical risk and associated financial impacts. This is increasingly cascading into real economy requirements. For example, listed companies in the UK, are already subject to mandatory disclosures (BEIS, 2022). This is further developing with the Transition Plan Taskforce is proposing listed and large companies disclose “objectives and priorities for responding and contributing to the transition towards a low-GHG emissions, climate-resilient economy” and setting out a roadmap of actions (Transition Plan Taskforce, 2023).

A key challenge for real economy entities is identifying where to allocate resources, in terms of managing their own risks but also looking for opportunities for new adaptation goods and services. An AIP can help in identifying both of these elements and could help the discussions and collaboration between public and private, including the role that Governments expect businesses to play. And where governments can act to support and encourage private investment, through improved enabling conditions or the strategic use of blended finance. The presence of such processes can in turn provide assurance to financial institutions that firms are managing their risks and contributing to financial stability, and to credit ratings agencies that governments are reducing future climate-related financial risks and liabilities.

Finally, investment planning can add structure and detail to the kinds of investments that ought to qualify as adaptation investments. A number of efforts have been made to develop such criteria. This includes the EU Sustainable Finance Taxonomy, but also proprietary standards (e.g. Standard Chartered, 2024). However, such approaches have encountered methodological challenges, including determining what constitutes an investment towards adaptation (Spacey Martin et al., 2024). Evaluating the alignment of the outputs from AIPs with

taxonomies should help financial institutions test and refine them to improve data quality as well as providing valuable insights on private sector adaptation finance flows.

4.2. Possible challenges in future implementation

Whilst the new approach has many novel features which may yield benefits, there are some drawbacks which may make its implementation challenging. For example, the positioning of the AIC as supporting activities within the wider adaptation cycle (in this case Regional Resilience Journey) may make it more challenging to understand and implement in practice, whilst the technical complexities of some tasks (particularly the use of economic thinking and appraisal to sequence adaptation over time) may require additional capacity building and training activities to ensure regions have the relevant skills to implement. In addition, the additional activities envisaged will also require resources to implement as well as enhanced knowledge and understanding. Thus, whilst this initiative is seeking to address such challenges for the first 100 European regions through the facilitation of a large grant and a capacity building programme the move to implementation and the roll out to other regions is likely to require considerably more resources.

5. Conclusions

The authors have reviewed the current state-of-the-art of adaptation finance processes and developed a process for subnational governments in Europe to translate adaptation strategies into programmatic pipelines of investments.

As a systemic intervention which focuses on addressing barriers to adaptation finance, the Adaptation Investment Cycle offers significant potential to support implementation of Europe’s goal of creating 150 climate resilient regions and local authorities by 2030 in its Adaptation Mission. Although at an early stage, there is emerging evidence the process has the potential to promote innovation and yield increased finance mobilisations, though it has also identified some of the challenges to long-term, widespread adoption.

Whilst the approach draws on AIPs that have been developed for NAPs in developing countries – where there is more focus on international public adaptation finance - and applies in the European context (where focus is on domestic public finance and private), the theoretical underpinning means that with appropriate modifications it could also be relevant beyond Europe. Enhancing the role of subnational finance offers new avenues to mobilise domestic resources.

There are a number of areas which warrant further investigation amidst this rapidly evolving adaptation decision landscape. Firstly, whilst we have proposed an overarching framework, each task involves a range of detailed steps, each with technical issues. Examples include processes for consideration of risk allocation, economic and financial appraisal, and the creation of pipelines of bankable projects. Each of these is a rapidly evolving area. For example, since the research was undertaken, several projects and studies have commenced exploring the relative importance of enabling conditions (Climate Policy Initiative, 2024; London School of Economics, 2025; OECD, 2024), and these could be included in future iterations. There are also similar financing approaches being developed for mitigation (e.g. Nassiry and Dixon, 2025) which could be explored for their synergies. Finally, a fuller analysis of subnational adaptation plans may also yield additional insights for essential components, since these are likely to vary by hazard, sector and country and region. There is also the question of whether subnational governments will have the pre-requisite skills, knowledge and experience to apply the cycle. Pathways2Resilience is providing capacity building support to regions piloting the framework, but this is relatively limited, and more detailed support may be needed.

It is also important to recognise that the approach outlined here is heavily stylised – financing decisions in the real world are subject to a

wide range of vagaries, including local political priorities, ever fluctuating financial positions and changing near term contexts. In addition, the process does not exist in a vacuum and will need to co-exist alongside existing budgetary processes and priorities.

Finally, it is unclear - though unlikely - whether the application of the Adaptation Investment Cycle alone will be enough to overcome the barriers to adaptation and mobilise the finance required to bridge the adaptation finance gap. For example, it may not be sufficient to change the economic attractiveness of adaptation and instead changes to the discount rate in project economic appraisal, increased prioritisation of adaptation compared to other policy agendas may be required. Similarly, it may not be able to make investment attractive enough for private investors, suggesting the need for more public or blended finance or greater willingness to pay by the public.

In this context, further research to understand the effectiveness of the Adaptation Investment Cycle is critical. Over the next three years the Investment Cycle will be subject to widespread testing by 100 subnational governments in Europe. It will be important to evaluate the outcomes of this process to understand the potential for adaptation finance processes to contribute to closing the adaptation finance gap in Europe and beyond.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Kit England: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Paul Watkiss:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Alistair Hunt:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Konstantinos Dellis:** Writing – review & editing, Conceptualization. **Sam Barrett:** Writing – review & editing, Conceptualization. **Richard Taylor:** Writing – review & editing. **Stella Whittaker:** Writing – review & editing, Conceptualization.

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Declaration of competing interest

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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